

Ni-Cu/Al₂O₃ containing 0.1% CeO₂ : A New Catalyst for Dehydrogenation of Alcohols

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A highly active and selective catalyst containing 10% Ni-Cu (atomic ratio 7 : 3) supported on alumina and promoted with 0.1% cerium oxide was developed for dehydrogenation of secondary alcohols into corresponding ketones in vapour phase.

Syntheses of aldehydes and ketones are more diverse and extensive than the synthesis of any other class of compounds because they are valuable intermediates in organic synthesis. Most frequently such compounds are prepared from primary and secondary alcohols. Among oxidants generally, and transition metals in particular, Cr^{VI} and Mn^{VII} are most widely used¹. However, synthesis of carbonyl compounds by catalytic dehydrogenation is an easy and convenient method mainly for : (i) higher selectivity, (ii) easy or no work-up, (iii) milder conditions and (iv) operationally simple to perform.

Many transition metals and their oxides possess catalytic activity. In some cases the metals with their variable valency may form unstable intermediates, and in other cases they provide a suitable reaction surface. The transition metals, such as Pt², Cu³, Au⁴, Fe₂O₃⁵, ZnO⁶, or Ni⁷, or a combination of such metals, e.g. Ru-ZnO⁸, Cu-ZnCr₂O₄⁹, Ni-Zn¹⁰, Zn-Cu¹¹, Cu-Co¹², CuO-Cr₂O₃¹³, ZnO-Cr₂O₃¹⁴, or Zn-Fe¹⁵ have been employed. These metals have also been supported on various supports, e.g. alumina¹⁶, magnesia¹⁷, silica¹⁸, graphite¹⁹, carbon²⁰, kieselguhr²¹, pumice²² or bentonite²³ in order to increase specific surface area and heat resistance, and sometimes promoted with K₂O²⁴, Na₂O²⁵ or ZrO₂²⁶ to achieve higher activity and selectivity.

Although a variety of catalysts have been employed for this purpose, the results were highly variable and depended critically upon, *inter alia*, substrate and reaction conditions. In this report we communicate the results of our investigations which led to the development of a new catalyst containing Ni-Cu on alumina and promoted with cerium oxide.

2-Octanol was chosen as a substrate for evaluating dehydrogenation activity of the catalyst. The unsupported catalysts were prepared by decomposing metal carbonates at 360° which were freshly precipitated from aqueous sulphate solutions with sodium hydrogen carbonate. Nevertheless, the supported catalysts were prepared either by physical mixing the carbonate and support or by coprecipitation method² followed by calcination. Each catalyst (10 g) was first reduced under a stream of hydrogen at 350° for 2 h and then assessed for its dehydrogenation activity by passing 2-octanol at the rate of 15 ml/h for 8 h at 185°.

Results and Discussion

Comparison of catalytic activities of transition metals : First it was decided to select one active transition metal which could be developed as a catalyst. Investigation of dehydrogenation

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activities of various transition metal catalysts under the same set of conditions revealed nickel to be more active than copper, cobalt, manganese or iron as shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1-DEHYDROGENATION ACTIVITIES OF TRANSITION METALS

Sl no	Catalyst	Space velocity v/v/s	2-Octanone %
1	Ni	0.0537	61.0
2	Cu	0.0851	53.0
3	Co	0.0425	36.0
4	Mn	0.0751	4.8
5	Fe	0.0751	2.4

The catalytical properties of metals have often been correlated with their electronic properties without arriving, however, at any direct correlation of universal validity²⁷. But it can be derived from the results obtained that higher number of atomic electrons and fcc type of structure of transition metals favour dehydrogenation activity. The mechanism of dehydrogenation of alcohols on transition metals has been studied in detail due to practical significance of the transformation. The process occurs through a carbonyl mechanism²⁸ as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Effect of support on the activity of Ni catalyst : Ni (10% by wt.) was loaded on magnesia, silica and alumina which exhibited different effects on its dehydrogenation activity

as shown in Table 2. The catalysts were prepared by physical mixing and surface area of alumina had no effect.

TABLE 2-EFFECT OF SUPPORTS ON DEHYDROGENATION ACTIVITY OF 10% Ni CATALYST

Sl no	Support	Space velocity v/v/s	2-Octanone %
1.	Magnesia	0.0851	32.5
2	Silica	0.0472	38.5
3	Alumina	0.0962	50.0

The nature of support is an important factor in governing the activity of a catalyst. It seems that neutral or slightly basic nature of alumina favours dehydrogenation reaction. IR studies have also shown that a support affects chemisorption of the molecules, therefore, rate of reaction²⁹. The method of catalyst preparation was varied but its dehydrogenation activity could not be improved.

Effect of Cu on Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst : Copper itself has been found to be less reactive, compared to nickel (Table 1) but when added as a promoter to Ni/alumina catalyst, a simultaneous decrease in catalytical activity was observed as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig 1

The detrimental effect of copper on Ni/alumina could be due to Ni-Cu alloy formation³⁰. Furthermore, copper is easy to reduce and may promote the reducibility of the accompanying metals³¹. The interactions of Ni-Cu have also

been studied by Auger spectroscopy which suggest that percentage *d*-character declines sharply as the concentration of copper increases³². Thus change in suitable metallic sites and electronic interactions are responsible for the observed behaviour of copper.

Effect of rare earth oxides on the activity of Ni-Cu/Al₂O₃ catalyst : Although copper had diminishing effect on Ni/alumina catalyst; 10% Ni-Cu (atomic ratio, 7 : 3) supported on alumina was arbitrarily chosen to study the effects of lanthanum oxide, cerium oxide and thorium oxide. These oxides were physically mixed with the catalyst in the concentrations of 0.1, 1.0 and 5.0% by wt. (based on Ni-Cu) and their effects were examined as summarised in Table 3.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF RARE EARTH OXIDES ON 10% Ni-Cu/Al₂O₃ CATALYST*

Sl. no.	Rare earth oxide	% by wt	2-Octanone %
1.	Lanthanum oxide	0.1	52.6
		1.0	53.7
		5.0	54.8
2.	Cerium oxide	0.1	54.1
		1.0	54.1
		5.0	50.9
3.	Thorium oxide	0.1	51.5
		1.0	51.7
		5.0	55.3

*Space velocity = 0.982 v/v/s.

All the rare earth oxides studied, i.e. La₂O₃, CeO₂ and ThO₂ show activating effect on the catalyst. However, at low concentrations (0.1%) cerium oxide had maximum effect. Schaper *et al.*³³ suggested that γ -alumina sinters by surface diffusion mechanism and lanthanum oxide prevents sintering by the formation of lanthanum aluminate layer on the surface. However, contradictory results have been found in which no such compound formation has been detected but it was found to improve the reducibility of Ni and its specific surface area. It is also suggested that lanthanum oxide layer over surface of alumina prevents the interactions between Ni and γ -alumina, making more Ni available on the surface³⁴. The addition

of cerium oxide increases the overall rate of reduction of NiO but at higher concentrations the rate decreases. It is also a better agent than lanthanum oxide to inhibit sintering of alumina. Thorium oxide also inhibits sintering of alumina and increases thermal stability³⁵.

Since 0.1% CeO₂ containing catalyst gave maximum conversions, it was selected to study the effect of metal loading. When total metal content was raised to 20% from 10%, the activity of the catalyst did not improve appreciably (57.4% instead of 54.1%). Thus, 10% Ni-Cu on alumina containing 0.1% CeO₂ as promoter was chosen to study the effect of temperature. And when the temperature of the catalyst bed was increased to 250°, the conversion rose to 86% with 97% selectivity. Other secondary alcohols also furnished excellent yields of ketones as shown in Table 4.

TABLE 4—DEHYDROGENATION OF SECONDARY ALCOHOLS ON 10% Ni-Cu/Al₂O₃ PROMOTED WITH 0.1% CeO₂

Sl. no.	Substrate	Space velocity v/v/s	Product	Yield %	Other products* (yield %)
1.		86			
2.		90			
3.	(10)				
4.	(5) (2.7)				

*The balance material is unreacted starting alcohol.

In this way a new catalyst was developed which showed high activity and selectivity as well as stability and should be useful in carrying out vapour phase dehydrogenations of secondary alcohols.

Experimental

The following instruments were used for

spectral/analytical data : Perkin-Elmer Infracord 267; Perkin-Elmer R32 (90 MHz) nmr spectrometer; Hewlett-Packard 5712A and 7624A gas chromatographs (ss columns, 360 × 0.6 cm; support, 60–80 mesh Chromosorb W; stationary phase, 10% Carbowax 20M; carrier gas, H₂); NFT-51 teflon spinning-band fractionation column (48 × 0.8 cm; theoretical plates, 80); Rajdhani RSMA-3 moisture balance equipped with 240 V IR lamp; Cadmach rotary tablet machine, type 16, station model CMD-3.

All reaction products are known compounds. These compounds were distilled, purity checked by gc and their identification established by ir and pmr spectra.

Alumina of different surface areas was supplied by United Catalysts India Ltd., Nandesari, and silica gel, without binder, 100–200 mesh was obtained from Centron and used without further purification. Magnesia was prepared according to a known procedure³⁶.

Catalyst activity testing unit : A fixed bed type of apparatus was employed for the evaluation of catalytical activity. A glass tubular reactor (84.0 × 2.0 cm) was filled with solid glass beads (dia. 0.4–0.5 cm) from bottom upto the height of 36.0 cm which acted as support, and up to the height of 13.0–15.0 cm, 10 g catalyst pellets were packed. Rest of the reactor was packed with glass beads serving as preheater zone. The reactor was placed vertically in a tubular furnace which had controlled heating system. The addition assembly was placed on the top of the reactor. The bottom-end of reactor rested on doubly bent tube which securely fitted in the receiver. Dry hydrogen gas which bubbled through conc. sulphuric acid was passed through the reactor at the rate of 50–60 ml/min. The furnace was heated with the help of Dimmerstat to a preset temperature of 350°. During the process, initially when temperature had reached about 180°, some water collected in the receiver, then hydrogen flow almost ceased (temp. 250–280°)

which after 30 min became normal. The catalyst was reduced for a period of 2 h when water stopped collecting. For the supported catalyst 0.25–0.30 ml and for unsupported catalyst 1.4–1.5 ml water was collected. When reduction was complete, the temperature was lowered to 185° and hydrogen flow adjusted to 10–12 ml/min. Alcohol was added dropwise from the addition assembly at the constant rate of 15 ml/h for a period of 8 h. The receiver was kept chilled throughout the experiment and aliquot collected after each hour through sampling device and analysed by gc.

Preparation of Ni-Cu/Al₂O₃ catalyst promoted with CeO₂ : Nickel sulphate (6.40 g, 0.02385 mol) and copper sulphate (2.356 g, 0.00943 mol) were dissolved in water (90 ml) at 68–90° and solution was allowed to cool to ~ 55° ambiently. The precipitation was then carried out by adding solid sodium hydrogen carbonate (6.15 g, 0.07323 mol) in several portions (~10) during 10–15 min. During this process the temperature of slurry dropped to ~ 50° and pH became 8.3. It was additionally digested for 1 h at the maintained temperature of 52–55°. It was then filtered and cake so obtained was washed with warm water (52–55°) several times (14 × 150 ml) to make it free from SO₄²⁻ ions and dried. The dried powder was then physically mixed with alumina (18 g; surface area 15–20 m² g⁻¹), carboxymethyl cellulose (0.6 g; 3%), magnesium borate (0.6 g; 3%), and cerium oxide (0.002 g; 0.1% based on Ni–Cu). The moisture content of this mixture was adjusted to 10–12% and after mixing with graphite (0.4 g; 2.0%) pelleted (dia. 0.5 × 0.3 cm). The pelleted catalyst so obtained was then calcined in a muffle furnace at 360° for 4.0 h, and 22.0 g catalyst was obtained.

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